

European Advanced Reusable Satellite Mission Engineering

Giovanni Medici^a, Raquel Marey Oton^a, Jaime Gutierrez Briceño^a,
Gabriele De Zaiacomò^a

^aDeimos Engineering and Systems SLU, Calle Francia 9, Puertollano, 13500, España

Abstract

The new launchers concepts and families dramatically reduced the cost of access to space. The satellite industry itself is adapting quickly to the new opportunity, bringing completely new classes of spacecrafts or systems such as small-sat constellations. On the other hand, more and more concerns are rising about the environmental sustainability of this 21st century gold rush. Leveraging on the experience of CNR, VKI, Deimos, Kongsberg Nanoavionics, T4i and University of Padova, the European Advanced Reusable Satellite (EARS) project, funded by the EC under the Horizon Europe program GA 101082531, aims to design and build a low-cost spacecraft capable of supporting a variety of small experiments for orbital missions potentially longer than a year. The satellite has to operate and return to Earth autonomously, taking advantage of a deployable/inflatable drag device and heatshield. After recovery, it shall be reused with minimal refurbishment. Moreover, it must be compatible with common launch vehicles secondary payload attachments. The spacecraft is based on a current microsatellite platform with the addition of a heat shield, a powerful propulsion system, and a recovery system (a parafoil – catcher solution).

This paper presents the mission engineering activities carried out to identify a promising solution in terms of the concept of operations, platform, and heatshield design parameters. The design process included multiple activities in support to the mission and system design: from de-orbit analysis to local entry corridor. Taking advantage of Deimos' heritage on inflatable decelerators, and leveraging on literature review, a preliminary assessment on the masses and volumes requirements for the flexible thermal protection system was carried out. The outcome of such activity is fundamental for the definition of the main parameters of the aeroshape, an enabler for the

identification of aerodynamic, aerothermodynamic and flying qualities performance, aiming to the definition of the reference trajectory.

Keywords: inflatable, deployable, heat-shield, decelerator, reusable, microsatellite

1 Introduction

The objective of the current study, within the frame of the European Advanced Reusable Satellite (EARS) project, is to establish the mission requirements for a reusable satellite, capable of supporting a variety of small experiments for orbital periods potentially exceeding a year. The vehicle must be designed for autonomous operation and return to Earth, and shall be reusable with minimal refurbishment. Furthermore, it should be compatible with common launch vehicles' secondary payload attachments. The satellite itself will be built upon an existing platform, developed by Kongsberg Nanoavionics. Two options have been considered: M16P and MP42. To achieve reusability, several additional systems and modules are required, in particular: **heat shield**, **propulsion** and **recovery systems**.

Figure 1: M16P platform

Figure 2: MP42 platform

Table 1: Vehicle parameters - Platform M16P

Vehicles parameters – M16P	
Mass	$m_0 = 20 - 40 \text{ kg}$
Nose radius (rigid TPS)	$r_{nose} = 0.3041 \text{ m}$
Dimensions	0.215x0.215x0.429

Table 2: Vehicle parameters - Platform MP42

Vehicles parameters – MP42	
Mass	$m_0 = 60 - 120 \text{ kg}$
Nose radius (rigid TPS)	$r_{nose} = 0.707 \text{ m}$
Dimensions	0.5x0.5x1.3*

* Maximum allowable height

This paper presents the definition of the entire mission profile, which in turn provides key elements towards the definition of various subsystems, including GNC, and the heat shield modules.

Section 2 provides an in-depth review of the state of the art, crucial for outlining the pros and cons of a flexible heatshield solution designed for Micro/Small satellites. The subsequent Mission Engineering section, briefly focuses on the analyses conducted to narrow down the solution domain to identify a promising design solution tailored to the EARS project. The final section provides an overview on the lessons learned during the analysis and design activities.

2 Literature Review

Inflatable or deployable heat shields have gained increasing prominence in recent years within the realm of designs and developments. The flexibility they offer presents numerous advantages for re-entry vehicles when compared to conventional rigid systems. These shield types can be compactly accommodated during launch, simplifying the design effort to cope with launcher-imposed usable volume limitations. The stowed or folded configuration allows for high packaging ratios.

Prior to entry, the heatshield is either inflated or deployed, thereby exposing the surface of the flexible thermal protection system (FTPS) to the hypersonic flow. This action significantly reduces the vehicle's ballistic coefficient. The primary advantage of this approach lies in the reduction of peak heat flux, as the deceleration occurs earlier during the return phase within the less dense, upper atmosphere. In contrast, rigid heat shields are constrained by the usable volume at launch, limiting their exposed surface area.

2.1 Inflatable Heat Shields

NASA is one of the main contributors to the development of a Hypersonic Inflatable Aerodynamic Decelerator (HIAD). The agency has undertaken missions like IRVE [1], [2], [3], [4] and HEART [5] to address key challenges posed by the HIAD program. Through these programs NASA has showcased various aspects of inflatable technology during Earth re-entry through sounding rocket campaigns. The most notable challenges were surviving the heat during atmospheric re-entry, demonstrating system performance at different scales, and demonstrating controllability in the atmosphere.

Figure 3: IRVE-3 vehicle configuration [2]

Figure 4: HEAT vehicle configuration [5]

The efforts of developing an inflatable heat shield continued with the LOFTID project, where NASA was able to perform the first orbital re-entry flight of the HIAD. The vehicle consisted of a 6 m inflatable structure, constructed with a stack of pressurized concentric rings, or torii, strapped together to form a blunt 140 ° cone-shaped structure [6]. This is the largest blunt body aeroshell to ever go through atmospheric entry.

Europe is also dedicating efforts to investigate these technologies: in the EFESTO project which is aimed to develop its own inflatable decelerator. The vehicle is depicted in Figure 5. Those are relatively high momentum projects, but there have been also private companies / start-ups leveraging on inflatable technologies. Andrew Space, for instance, manage to build an inflatable heat shield for a CubeSat [7].

Figure 5: EFESTO system configuration for Earth applications [8]

2.2 Deployable Heat Shields

Deployable heat shields are extensively researched for various applications, including Earth, and Mars entry [9] and there are even conceptual designs for potential Venus missions [10]. NASA is actively investing substantial efforts in developing a deployable heat shield. In 2018, the agency successfully executed a sub-orbital flight of the ADEPT vehicle [11], [12], making a significant achievement. ADEPT is a concept that incorporates a series of deployable ribs and struts, connected with a flexible fabric skin. When deployed, this configuration behaves as a semi-rigid aeroshell entry system with a 70-degree sphere cone shape, Figure 6.

Figure 6: ADEPT-SR1 configurations [13]

The Italian Space Agency is also working on different concepts of deployable shields, with MINI-IRENE [14], [15], MISTRAL [16] or IPERDRONE [17] projects. The research efforts are not limited to agencies and private companies, the topic is actively researched also by academics, as for instance, the Imperial College of London, that worked on a concept to land large payloads in Mars [18].

2.3 Conclusions

Table 3 provides an overview on the main conclusions that can be drafted from the literature review performed in the current section. It is key to remark that the two solutions have strong and weak points, and applicability depends very much on the case analysed. On the other hand, the maturity level, and public information available for the inflatable heatshield, assists the engineer in the preliminary design phases; many considerations in this paper root in the inflatables. Moreover, its modular nature is a remarkable asset for a consortium project like EARS, where each partner contributes with its technical skills. Therefore a small edge for the inflatable technology was identified for the EARS configuration.

Table 3: Inflatable and deployable heatshield comparison.

Inflatable heatshields	Deployable heatshields
Used mainly for heavy satellites	Extensive study for smaller satellites
Successfully tested in orbit (LOFTID)	Sub-orbital tests (ADEPT)
More public information regarding the mass budget for the heat shield	Limitations on the public information regarding the mass budget
Worse packing density values	No definite data available, nevertheless it is expected to provide slightly favourable packing density values.
Large volume usage	The deployable arms normally don't take volume, when located in the satellite faces, but need thermal protection. This can also lead to a drift from the conventional U shape factor.
Easier to adapt to non-cylindrical structures	Need for a structure to adapt/interface the rectangular/cubic shape to a circular one.
Easier stowing, easier integration with the solar panels	More difficult to stow the FTSP cloth, less likely the integration with solar panels
Modular design	Requires integral design with the structure

3 EARS re-entry Mission Engineering

The Mission Engineering goal is to define the entire mission profile, from the initial operational orbit down to the descent phase (Figure 7). From a given set of **initial conditions (0)** the **de-orbit analysis (1)** is carried out. The de-orbit phase finishes when the so-called Entry Interface Point (EIP), located 120 km above Earth's surface, is reached. At EIP the process hands-over to the **Local Entry Corridor (LEC) analysis (2)**. This study provides the feasible flight envelope, the region defined in terms of entry flight path angle and ballistic coefficient able to withstand the re-entry loads. The **reference trajectory (3)** is defined by selecting the most promising values (γ_{EIP} , BC) from the feasible region of the LEC. Both the de-orbit and LEC analysis are going to be performed for the two satellite platforms, M16P and MP42.

Figure 7: Rationale of the mission analysis

3.1 De-orbit analysis

The de-orbit analysis defines the spacecraft's transition from its operational orbit to the entry interface point (EIP). This manoeuvre is initiated by a de-orbit burn at a specific point along the nominal orbit, so to transfer the spacecraft onto an entry ellipse. The elliptical orbit has the low-lying periapsis intersecting the EIP at a designated flight path angle, γ_{EIP} . The timing and position of the burn must be meticulously chosen, to ensure the spacecraft arrives at the EIP within the desired window, enabling accurate targeting of the predefined landing site. The primary objective of the de-orbit analysis is to calculate the necessary fuel for executing this manoeuvre and the final conditions achieved at the EIP (flight path angle and velocity).

The initial orbit is assumed to be circular, with an altitude of $h = 300$ km, and

two de-orbit scenarios are considered, equatorial and SSO. The propulsion system is assumed to be the same for both satellite platforms, $T = 10 \text{ N}$ and $I_{sp} = 250 \text{ s}$. During this manoeuvre is assumed that the heat shield is not deployed yet, and the drag coefficient is the one of the satellite, assuming $C_d = 2.2$.

The de-orbit analysis is performed for both orbital scenarios, **Equatorial** and **Sun Synchronous Orbit (SSO)**, for a **range of masses** that considers both satellite platforms, M16P and MP42, and for a **range of ΔV** applied to perform the manoeuvre (equivalent to the de-orbit fuel consumed). The initial orbit has a significant impact in the FPA achieved at the EIP, reaching steepest values in the equatorial scenario. The satellite mass has also a minor effect on the FPA, leading to shallower values the heavier the satellite is. The de-orbit fuel, on the other hand, increases with the satellite mass, but remains constant within scenarios, as it only depends on the ΔV and the specific impulse of the engine. In the SSO de-orbit, which is the most demanding scenario, the velocity achieved at the EIP is considerably higher. SSO results in elevated re-entry conditions, due to its greater velocities. As will be discussed later, this phenomenon will have implications for the Local Entry Corridor. The de-orbit time is influenced both by the spacecraft mass and the orbit scenario. As one might anticipate, the de-orbit time decreases with an increase in the ΔV (de-orbit fuel).

Figure 8: Flight path angle at the EIP as function of the fuel consumed.

Figure 9: Velocity at the EIP as function of the fuel consumed.

For its nature, the mission engineering process should be iterative. The feasibility region defined by the LEC must be achievable through the de-orbit analysis, and if not, another analysis loop is needed. The new iteration varies other mission parameters to check whether it is possible to fulfil the specified EIP conditions. This situation pertained to the SSO scenario. During the LEC analysis it became evident that the feasible flight path angles did not align with those projected from the previously examined de-orbit maneuver. Consequently, it became necessary to adjust certain initial conditions. This adjustment aimed to determine whether the SSO scenario could be made feasible without compromising the fuel consumption or necessitating an excessive augmentation of the propulsion system.

- **ΔV increase:** The first modification was an increase in the ΔV range, up until 300 m/s, and it was possible to achieve higher the FPA at the EIP. For the heavier satellite option (MP42) aside from a higher ΔV it is also necessary a larger amount of thrust ($T > 10$ N). The M16P configuration requires an increased ΔV , more than 170 m/s, to achieve a FPA compliant with the LEC for the SSO scenario.
- **Thrust increase:** There were some cases where the thrusting time was too large and the EIP was reached before engines burnout. An increase in thrust reduces the time, allowing the satellite to perform the entire thrusting manoeuvre. At least 25 N of thrust are needed to guarantee the de-orbit in all of the scenarios.
- **Lower De-orbit altitude:** In addition to the increase in ΔV , the impact of altering the de-orbit altitude was also investigated. Initially, a reduction in altitude, to $h = 200$ km was examined. For this particular scenario, it was assumed that the heat shield was deployed, and the initial part of the de-orbit, from 300 km to 200 km, was performed using the aerodynamic drag. Consequently, for this study the drag coefficient used was $C_d = 1.5$. The decrease in the initial de-orbit altitude adversely affects the final flight path angle achieved at the EIP. Furthermore, extended deployment of the heat shield over a prolonged duration raises concerns about potential damage or misalignment of the system.
- **Higher De-orbit altitude:** An increase in the de-orbit altitude was also studied. A rise in the orbit altitude requires a higher ΔV to perform the maneuver. At higher altitudes, with 100 m/s is not possible

anymore to de-orbit the satellite. Furthermore, more de-orbit time is required. The only benefit foreseen of a higher initial altitude is to obtain a steeper FPA with the same amount of fuel consumed.

3.2 Local Entry Corridor

The Local Entry Corridor is a 2-D analysis based on multiple trajectories simulations covering a parametric variation of:

- Entry Flight Path Angle, γ_{EIP}
- Ballistic Coefficient, $\beta = \frac{m}{C_D \cdot S_{ref}}$

The objective of the analysis is to determine the feasible region in terms of the design parameters (γ_{EIP} and BC) to ensure that the re-entry of spacecraft happens in a safe range of structural and aerothermal parameters and the vehicle is able to reach the landing point. To determine this feasible region, it is explored a domain of $n \times m$ (n the number of γ_{EIP} values and m the number of BC points) 3dof re-entry trajectories, starting from the EIP and ending at ground. These trajectories are calculated for a set of worst-case conditions for both the atmosphere and the vehicle aerodynamics. The atmospheric model is the USSA1976, with 3σ dispersions, and for the drag coefficient a representative value of the hypersonic leg is taken, $C_D = 1.5 \pm 20\%$. Furthermore, during the re-entry no winds are considered.

The constraints defined for the mission are the variables that identify the mission feasible domain. As it still is an early phase in the project, there are no hard boundaries defined thus far, yet, leveraging on heritage it is possible to outline the following guideline values:

- Dynamic Pressure: 12 kPa
- Heat Load: 40 MJ/m² (for Flexible TPS)
- Heat Flux: 450 kW/m² (for Flexible TPS)
- Load factor: 12 g
- Landing accuracy: 150 km

The LEC analysis is performed separately for both orbital scenarios as the re-entry velocity of the SSO is much higher ($V \sim 7900$ m/s) than the one of equatorial scenario ($V \sim 7450$ m/s). The **SSO scenario** is therefore more **constraining**. As a result, its feasible region is smaller than for the equatorial

scenario. Moreover, the flight path angles needed to perform a safe re-entry are much steeper, requiring a high ΔV (increase in the fuel consumption) and thrust to achieve the **feasible Local Entry Corridor**. Furthermore, in this scenario, shallow flight path angles lead to **skip re-entry** ($\gamma_{EIP} > -1.5^\circ$). Furthermore, the two satellite platforms possess a distinct nose radii, which directly influences the heat flux values encountered during re-entry. The higher the nose radius, the smaller the heat flux. The MP42 platform has a higher nose radius, enabling higher BC values, and thus allowing for smaller heat shield sizes.

3.3 Promising configuration

Among the proposed scenarios for the mission baseline, an equatorial orbit and the MP42 platform represents the most promising configuration. The SSO de-orbit conditions are hardly achievable, and the re-entry loads are severe, making it difficult to obtain a feasible LEC. The current baseline therefore focuses on Equatorial. The bigger satellite platform, MP42 resulted the most promising. This spacecraft is more likely to fit the payload, re-entry and descent module. The heat shield configuration (nose radius) for this satellite is more likely to withstand re-entry loads.

Regarding the heat shield, there is more public information available for inflatable heat shields, allowing to easily obtain a preliminary sizing of the shield. The design of a deployable heat shield is highly integrated in the satellite structure, requiring a high level of decision making, making it more difficult to have a preliminary configuration. Therefore, the following heatshield preliminary sizing is obtained assuming an **inflatable heat shield**. The main driver of the heat shield size is the ballistic coefficient and is the heat flux what limits this value. The constraint of 450 kW/m^2 can be increased, because the trajectory simulation gives the value for the stagnation point. The nose cap of the heat shield can be made of ceramic materials, capable of withstanding higher heat fluxes. Being conservative, the nose cap can face up to 600 kW/m^2 , but in the upcoming aerothermodynamic analysis must be guaranteed that the flexible TPS (conical part of the shield) the heat fluxes are below 450 kW/m^2 .

The design space is limited by the de-orbit manoeuvre. The selected baseline applies 100 m/s of ΔV , to de-orbit the spacecraft from its operational orbit, a 300 km circular and equatorial orbit. With these nominal conditions the flight path angle at the EIP is $\gamma_{EIP} = -1.6519^\circ$. It is also important to have a first estimation of what can be the dispersion in the FPA, that's why is assumed a

variation of the $\pm 2.5\%$ on the ΔV ($\Delta V = 100 \text{ m/s} \pm 2.5\%$), leading to a variability of the $\pm 0.04^\circ$ in the FPA. With the nominal entry flight path angle, it is easier to select a ballistic coefficient. As design point is chosen $BC = 28 \text{ kg/m}^2$, a value that can provide a small heat shield without being too close to the heat flux limit.

Figure 10: LEC for the equatorial scenario of MP42 platform

3.4 Heatshield preliminary sizing

Leveraging on the outcomes of the previous analysis (as well as from the datasheet of MP42 configuration), it is possible to define high level set of requirements to draft the aeroshape of the deployed/inflated heatshield. The peculiar versatility of the MP42 platform allows for an adjustable customers payload, up to 1.3 m. Within the context of this project, the platform versatility was used so to mock-up the widest volume envelope as possible, therefore allowing fitting the rigid and flexible heatshield, the payload, the bus, recovery and propulsion systems. It shall be remarked though that the current, widest, configuration is suboptimal from a mission perspective; as it will likely expose to higher fluxes the back-shell, as well as set apart the cog from the nose of the vehicle, therefore impacting the overall aerodynamic and stability performance, nevertheless, should the payload bus and recovery system volume needs decrease, the blue volume of Figure 12 can be reduced as well, therefore helping mitigating impinging and stability issues.

Figure 11: MP42 Payload Envelope. *Satellite height is highly adjustable to customers payload requirements, up to 1300 mm (Courtesy of Kongsberg NanoAvionics)

The heat shield mass was determined through volumetric scaling of the system mass, using comparable inflatable heat shield missions, LOFTID, HEART and EFESTO. Among these missions, EFESTO features the smallest diameter, making its scaling values the most reliable benchmark. The results of this scaling procedure are presented in Table 4. The current estimated mass heat shield mass is approximately 13 kg. For practical implementation, the inflatable structure and flexible TPS need to be stowed in the satellite. To calculate the necessary volume for stowing the fabrics, a conservative value of packing density, $\rho_{packing} = 200 \text{ kg/m}^3$ [19], was used.

Table 4: EARS heat shield preliminary mass estimation.

Component	Mass Estimation (kg)
Inflatable Structure + FTPS	8.32
Rigid nose (RTPS)	3.54
Inflation System (CGG)	0.8
Heat shield mass estimation	12.66

To size the inflation system, a tension cone configuration was assumed for the heat shield. Knowing the gas volume and the inflation pressure, required gas mass to fill the inflatable structure can be straightforwardly obtained. Assuming that the gas used is N_2 , the mass required is around 70 g. Looking at cold gas generators specification sheets [20] it is seen that to generate this mass of N_2 , 2 CGG are required, weighting 400 g each. Table 5 summarizes the design parameters for the aeroshape and the bus, payload, and heatshield bays.

Table 5: Aeroshape design parameters

Parameter	dimension	Unit
Deployed Diameter	1.867	m
Nose Radius	0.707	m
Cone Angle	60°	degrees
Stowed FTPS bay	0.16x0.5x0.5	m
Payload bay (up to bus	0.91	m
bus	0.23	m

Figure 12, on the other hand sketches the deployed configuration of the aeroshape. The black section refers to the rigid heatshield spherical nose section, which is connected to the yellow conical part, of the heatshield, which is clothed with Flexible Thermal Protection System (FTPS).

Figure 12: Heatshield preliminary sizing

The parameters reported in Table 5 are a direct follow up of the analysis carried out in the previous sections. The diameter constraint is limited on one side by the (highest) feasible ballistic coefficient, and on the other hand by the constraint to minimize the expected FTPS fabric needs. The bigger the nose radius, the lower the peak heat fluxes, on the other hand there are limitations on the maximum surface allocation for the rigid heatshield spherical section (interface with the rest of the MP42 platform). Literature review, for Earth applications show little variability as far as cone angles is

concerned. The usual values range between 45° and 60° , being 45° the most stable (and less efficient, from a mass standpoint), and 60° a good compromise in terms of stability and mass efficiency. As it was observed in section 3.2, the nose radius is a limiting constraint: LEC is closed by heat flux constraint. Therefore, the cone angle choice of 60° is also maximizing the nose radius, as the maximum dimension of the rigid heatshield is limited by the platform base area.

3.5 Reference trajectory

The reference trajectory is obtained for the equatorial scenario of the MP42 platform, with an initial mass of 115.2 kg, where it is already subtracted the fuel mass from the de-orbit burn, $m_{fuel} = 4.8$ kg. The initial flight path angle, given by the de-orbit analysis, is $\gamma_{EIP} = -1.6519^\circ$. It was used a preliminary aero database, obtained through modified Newtonian, for a heatshield size of $D = 1.8687$ m. The atmosphere model utilized is the USSA1976. Figure 13 shows the velocity altitude envelope of the reference trajectory according to the previous assumptions. Due to the re-entry from an equatorial orbit at 300 km of altitude, the reference trajectory differs with respect to a typical Shuttle re-entry. The figure provides an indication of the aerothermodynamic state of the gas during entry, and therefore some aerothermodynamics effects can be expected. The trajectory experience all the main phenomenon, nitrogen and oxygen dissociation and vibrational excitation.

Figure 13: Velocity altitude envelope for the reference trajectory

The evolution of the main aerothermodynamic parameters is shown in Figure 14, Figure 15, Figure 16 and Figure 17. As expected, all the variables are compliant with the constraints. The maximum value for the dynamic pressure and load factor is reached at 200 s in the trajectory, around 60 km of altitude. The peak for the heat flux occurs earlier, at 165 s.

Figure 14: Dynamic Pressure evolution

Figure 15: Load Factor evolution

Figure 16: Heat Flux evolution

Figure 17: Heat Load evolution

4 Conclusions

The main outcomes of the Mission Engineering activity for the EARS project are described in the paragraphs that follows.

The literature research justifies the values in terms of packaging densities and constraints that were used in the de-orbit analysis and local entry corridor. More publicly available data on inflatables technology was found when compared to deployables.

Among the two platforms analysed, M-16P and MP-42, the second, bigger one is the only one identified to fit the Mission Requirements in terms of payload and load envelope. The current baseline calls for Equatorial trajectories, as SSO is a worst-case scenario, and the shallow FPA lead likely to skip-outs. The current design is compatible with an inflatable system. With a rigid heatshield and cone angle of 60° , to foster longitudinal aerodynamic stability in the hypersonics and a light efficient design.

A reference trajectory, based on a preliminary aerodynamic database, was identified. Smaller ballistic coefficient implies bigger heatshield surface, which conversely calls for higher entry mass.

In conclusion, the comprehensive analysis process outlined in this paper, which encompassed literature research, de-orbit analysis, Local Entry Corridor, and heatshield design, has distilled into the formulation of the Mission System Requirements of the project.

A Acknowledgments

Funded by the
European Union

Figure 18: Funded by the European Union.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe's research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101082531. Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

This project represents a collaborative endeavor coordinated by Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR), and relies on the contribution and expertise of T4i, Kongsberg Nanoavionics, Università degli Studi di Padova, Von Karman Institute, and Deimos Engineering and Systems. The authors want to express their sincere gratitude to the contributions and expertise of these partners, which greatly enhance the progress and potential of this ongoing study.

References

- [1] R. Dillman, S. Hughes, R. Bodkin, D. Bose and J. Del Corso, “Flight Performance of the Inflatable Re-entry Vehicle Experiment II”.
- [2] R. Dillman, “Flight Performance of the Inflatable Re-entry Vehicle Experiment 3,” Nasa, 18 August 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/80604887.pdf>. [Accessed 15 June 2023].
- [3] R. Dillman, J. DiNonno, R. Bodkin, V. Gsell, N. Miller, A. Olds and W. Bruce, “Flight performance of the inflatable reentry vehicle experiment 3. In International Planetary Probe Workshop,” 2013.
- [4] D. Litton, D. Bose, F. Cheatwood, S. Hughes and H. Wright, “Inflatable re-entry vehicle experiment (IRVE)-4 overview,” *21st AIAA Aerodynamic Decelerator Systems Technology Conference and Seminar*.
- [5] H. Wright, A. Cutright, J. Corliss, W. Bruce and D. Trombetta, “HEART flight test overview,” in *9th International Planetary Probe Workshop*, France, 2012.
- [6] R. Dillman, J. DiNonno, Bodkin J and S. Hughes, “Planned Orbital Flight Test of a 6m HIAD,” in *International Planetary Probe Workshop*, Colorado, 2018.
- [7] J. Andrews, K. Watry and K. Brown, “Nanosat deorbit and recovery system to enable new missions,” 2011.
- [8] I. Dietlein, G. Guidotti, I. Pontijas Fuentes, F. Trovarelli, A. Rivero, T. Schleutker and S. Callsen, “Development of Inflatable Heat Shield Technology for Re-Entry Systems in EFESTO project,” in *9th European Conference For Aeronautics And Space Science, EUCASS*, 2022.

- [9] V. Ethiraj, K. Hamm and I. Fernandez, “Adaptive deployable entry and placement technology (ADEPT): a feasibility study for human missions to Mars,” in *21st AIAA Aerodynamic Decelerator Systems Technology Conference and Seminar*, 2011.
- [10] B. Smith, V. Ethiraj and P. Wercinski, “Venus In Situ Explorer Mission design using a mechanically deployed aerodynamic decelerator.,” in *IEEE Aerospace Conference*, 2013.
- [11] B. Smith, A. Cassell and C. Kruger, “Nano-ADEPT: An entry system for secondary payloads,” in *IEEE Aerospace Conference*, 2015.
- [12] A. Cassell, B. Smith, P. Wercinski, G. Shakib, H. Kenneth and A. Nelessen, “ADEPT, A Mechanically Deployable Re-Entry Vehicle System, Enabling Interplanetary CubeSat and Small Satellite Missions,” 2018.
- [13] A. Korzun, D. Soumyo, R. McDaniel and C. Karlgaard, “Aerodynamics for the ADEPT SR-1 Flight Experiment.,” AIAA Aviation, 2019.
- [14] R. Gardi, A. Fedele, G. Pezzella, P. Vernillo and R. Savino, “MINI-IRENE: Design of a deployable heat shield capsule for a sounding rocket flight experiment.,” in *Proceedings of the 68th international astronautical congress*, 2017.
- [15] R. Savino, R. Lo Forti and E. Bassano, “IRENE–Italian re-entry nacelle for microgravity experiments,” in *62nd International Astronautical Congress*, Cape Town (South Africa), 2011.
- [16] R. Fortezza, R. Savino and G. Russo, “Mistral (air-launched micro-satellite with reentry capability) a small spacecraft to carry out several missions in leo,” 2013.
- [17] S. Iannelli, M. Albano, M. Di Clemente and A. Gabrielli, “Iperdrone roadmap for new on orbit services performed by Space Drones,” in *Proceedings of the 70th International Astronautical Congress*, Washington DC, 2019.
- [18] L. Peacocke, P. Bruce and M. Santer, “Deployable Aero-Decelerator Heatshield Configuration,” in *International Astronautical Congress*, Australia, 2017.
- [19] I. Clark, A. Hutchings, C. Tanner and R. Braun, “Supersonic inflatable aerodynamic decelerators for use on future robotic missions to Mars,”

- in *IEEE Aerospace Conference*, 2008.
- [20] C. S. & Systems, *Cold Gas Generators for Space Applications*, 2014.